

HOUSE OF EDUCATION OF THE BUKHARA PEOPLE'S SOVIET REPUBLIC IN
MOSCOW.

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Annotation: This article highlights the creation and activities of the Bukhara House of Education in the city of Moscow.

Key words: Bukhara, "Bukhara House of Education", Representation of the BNSR, Mukamilov, F. Khodzhaev Spiridonovka.

After the overthrow of the power of the emir in late August - early September 1920, Bukhara was drawn into the sphere of interests of the Soviet government. The Bukhara People's Soviet Republic, which existed in 1920-1924, was important for the spread of the ideas of communism in the East.

At the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, Russia was the main partner in Bukhara's foreign policy. After the overthrow of the power of the Emir, Bukhara became an important testing ground for the policy of the Soviet government. For the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic, which existed in 1920-1924, cooperation in training personnel for the national economy was of great importance. The young republic, despite the enormous hardships of wartime and economic devastation, led fruitful cooperation in the field of education of Bukhara students with the Soviet republics of the RSFSR, the Turkestan ASSR, Azerbaijan, and Georgia. It should be noted that, in Soviet historiography, this problem was covered within the framework of the dominant Marxist-Leninist ideology. With the collapse of the USSR and the formation of independent states, it became possible to objectively and comprehensively scientifically study this issue. In our opinion, one of such topical issues is the cooperation between the BNSR and the RSFSR in the field of education and training. In this article, we will try to analyze some aspects of the activities of the "Bukhara House of Education" in the city of Moscow.

One of the main directions in the field of cultural cooperation was the training of personnel for the national economy and education of the BNSR with the RSFSR. For these purposes, the government of the BNSR took upon itself the financial support of the Bukhara students sent to Moscow [1:l.16.]. The list of the first batch of Bukhara students sent to Moscow was compiled on August 20, 1922 [2:l.20.]. In total there were 25 people, of which 20 Uzbeks, 3 Tatars, 2 Tajiks, the age of the younger was 16, the older was 22 [1:l.13.].

On September 12, 1922, students from Bukhara, under the leadership of the representative of the BNSR in the RSFSR Mukamilov, were sent to the city of Moscow and Petrograd [2:l.75.]. The Bukhara government did its best to expand mutual cooperation in the field of personnel training with the RSFSR. The plenipotentiary representative of the BNSR Mukamilov, in his letter addressed to the Deputy Commissar for Foreign Affairs L. Karakhan, described in detail the picture in the field of education in the BNSR, and asked for help by petitioning the RSFSR Education Commissariat to organize a school for Bukhara students in the amount of 100 boys, 25 girls in Moscow with the representation BNSR[3:l.16.]. During this period, Bukhara sent her children to receive education in the Transcaucasus and Germany. For example, in 1921, 30 students were sent to these states, in 1922, about 50 students were sent to Germany [3:l.16.]. The representative office of the Belarusian People's Republic in Moscow applied to the People's Commissariat for Foreign Affairs of the RSFSR to assist in the training of personnel for the

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national economy of Bukhara in educational institutions in Moscow. L. Karakhan, in his letter addressed to the then Commissar for Nationalities, I. Stalin, cited the above facts and offered, for his part, to open a small school for Bukhara children in Moscow at the expense of the BNSR government [3:l.94.]. In turn, the People's Commissar of Nationalities I. Stalin proposed to open a school for the children of Bukhara at the expense of the BNSR, to organize a group of 30-35 people in a communist university in the city of Moscow [3:l.111.].

By order of the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR in April 1923, the commissariats for nationalities and education were entrusted with organizing the Bukhara "House of Education" in Moscow. By decision of the RSC(b), the building of Sakhara-Trest No. 9 near the Kremlin became the first school in Bukhara in Moscow [4:l.121.]. At first, the school was intended for 75 people. With the increase in the number of students from Bukhara, there were not enough places in the building. Representatives of the BNSR in Moscow appealed to the accommodation commission under the government of the RSFSR to help determine a new location for the "House of Education" of the BNSR in the amount of 200 students. By decision of the commission dated July 9, 1923, No. 17, the house on Spiridonovka Street became a new place for the Bukhara "House of Education" [5:l.68.].

The Bukhara school began its work on August 25 at a new location by order of the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR dated August 21, 1923 No. 127 [4:l.121.]. The issues of renting this building were considered at a meeting of the real estate department of the city of Moscow on January 5, 1924. The lease term was set for a period of 6 years, the annual rent was 16,000 gold rubles, if we add here the cost of repairing the building, the BNSR had to pay 25,000 gold rubles every year [4:l.121.].

The government of the BNSR, headed by F. Khodzhaev, paid great attention to all spheres of activity of this school. The meeting devoted to this issue dated March 8, 1923 was attended by F. Khodzhaev, the plenipotentiary representative of Bukhara in the RSFSR M. Burkhanov, the chairman of the Supreme Council of Economics M. Mukhitdinov, the head of the trade department in Moscow G. Khodzhaev, the director of the cotton trust Belyakov, the head of the "House of Education" Fayzi. According to Faizi's report, decisions were made on issues such as the school budget, to form a commission for the supervision of funds, to strengthen control over the implementation of the budget, to determine measures for the recruitment of students from Bukhara youth, which stipulated that out of a hundred students 25 should be girls, to organize short-term courses at the "House of Education" [6: l.28.].

The difficult situation of that time associated with the civil war on the territory of the RSFSR and economic devastation had an impact on the activities of the school. The "House of Enlightenment" of Bukhara operated in difficult conditions. These difficulties consisted in the insufficiently established connection with the nazirat of education in Bukhara, all the activities of the school were carried out by the Moscow authorities, such as the board of trustees of the Krasny Vostok factory, the household and educational situation of the school did not meet elementary sanitary standards [4:l.145-152.]. Despite the economic difficulties and the high cost of food in the city of Moscow, the BNSR government and its bodies were able to regularly provide their students with everything they needed. If in September 1923, 12 gold rubles were spent to provide for one student, then at the beginning of 1924, 29 gold rubles were spent for these purposes [4:l.146.]. There were also shortcomings in providing students with food. The management of the Krasny Vostok factory used the money allocated for these purposes for their own needs. There

was not even elementary sanitary standards in the dining room. On February 13, 1924, the Consulate of the BNSR in Moscow sent a certain amount to improve the provision of food for students [4:l.147.].

In September 1923, Campenus developed a project for the expenses of the Bukhara "House of Education". It was planned to allocate 10,000 gold rubles for the repair of the building. The operation of funds allocated for the provision of the Bukhara school was carried out through intermediaries, such as the Krasny Vostok factory. The lack of control over the actions of this factory led to the fact that the factory used the funds allocated for the repair of the school for other purposes [4:l.147.]. In the "House of Education" there were not enough teachers and support staff to carry out a full-fledged educational process. In February 1924, to correct the difficult situation, the school management developed a new project of expenses in the amount of 68,000 gold rubles. The project, based on the norms of Moscow schools, provided for the allocation of 5 students per teacher, and a staff of medical staff was created to control the health of students. Subsequently, there were changes in the project. The expenses of the school for 9 months were determined in the amount of 65,000 gold rubles. According to the project developed by A. Zimmerman, an employee of the Nazirat of Education of the BNSR, all expenses of the "House of Education" for 9 months were to be 195,963 gold rubles [4:l.148.]. In the Bukhara school, people responsible for raising children used physical force and there were cases of sending children to work in the Zarai factory. The methods of education with the use of force by one of the leaders of the school, Burnashev, led to discontent among the students. Bukhara students consisting of 7 people were sent to the Zaraisk factory to familiarize themselves with the production. School leaders sent students to the factory for violations and used the work of students in production almost free of charge [4:l.148.]. To improve the financial situation of the Bukhara House of Education, a board of trustees was created after the formation of the Bukhara consul in Moscow by the chairmanship. After the formation, the Board of Trustees undertook to provide for the expenses of 54 students, each month in the amount of 500 gold rubles, i.e. 25% of all expenses of the "House of Education". Subsequently, cash receipts decreased to 45 gold rubles [4:l.149.].

By the way, Bukhara students studied in Germany, Turkey and Azerbaijan during this period. In the spring of 1923, a campaign began for the return of students from abroad, not without the participation of Soviet representatives. Despite all the difficulties, Moscow was the largest center for training personnel for the national economy of the BNSR. As of February 1924, only 172 students from Bukhara studied in Moscow. They were distributed in educational institutions in the following order:

Working faculty - 20 students.

1. In the cultural and educational sphere - 16 students.
2. Military school - 7 students.
3. There are 7 students in the Zaraisk factory.
4. Primary and secondary schools - 5 students.
5. There are 127 students in the "House of Education".

Of these, 50 students were planned to be placed in schools subordinate to the Moscow Department of Public Education [4:l.149-150.].

During the period under review, not only students from Bukhara studied in Moscow, but also at the beginning of 1924, students from Turkestan were trained in the amount of 400 people [4:l.149-150.]. The BNSR government and its representatives operating in Moscow tried with all

their might and means to help the “House of Education” operating in the city of Moscow. Despite the ongoing hostilities on the territory of Bukhara and the economic ruin, the government of the republic provided the school with everything necessary. A year after the formation of the "House of Education" in Bukhara in Moscow, successes and shortcomings, directions for improving the work of the school became obvious. Representatives of Bukhara intended to solve such topical issues as internal and external relations of the school. First of all, it was necessary to settle organizational issues by subordinating the school directly to the Nazirat of Education of the BNSR, to appoint an official responsible for constant communication with the Nazirat of National Education, to establish full control of the plenipotentiary representative over all the structures of the school, to bring the annual budget of the school to 200,000 gold rubles [4: 1.151-158.].

On May 18, 1924, the anniversary of the “House of Enlightenment” of Bukhara was celebrated in Moscow. It was decided to elect Stalin, Krupskaya, Chicherin, Khodzhaev honorary (homii) [4: 1.320.]. This was the first and last holiday in the history of the “House of Education” of the BNSR in Moscow. With the implementation of the national-state demarcation in Central Asia in the summer and autumn of 1924, the Bukhara People’s Soviet Republic disappeared from the political arena.

The political, economic and cultural ties between the BNSR and the RSFSR lasted only about 4 years. By historical standards, the period is very short and they have not always been smooth. The study of this scientific problem from the point of view of historical truth will serve to strengthen and develop mutually beneficial relations between modern Russia and Uzbekistan. Open up new opportunities for the emergence of innovative ideas for the rapprochement of our peoples in all spheres of public life. The study of international relations, especially economic and cultural ties, broaden the horizons of the younger generation, respect for the past, analyze and cognize the historical process in all its complexity and diversity, understand and respect the culture and worldview of other peoples. In our opinion, this is the main mission of historical science. By studying history, we bring people together.

Despite the difficult situation connected with the war and economic disruption, the policy of the BNSR government in the field of education is instructive even today. Instructive is the example of students sent to another country for education. A foreign country, a difficult situation, isolation from loved ones did not prevent people under 20 from getting a good education. Today's generation should take an example from the young people of a century ago.

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